

Reviewing The Potential of Snail Extract to Accelerate and Improve Burn Wound Healing: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Burn wounds present a significant challenge in medical treatment due to their complex healing processes and susceptibility to infection. Snail mucus, known for its regenerative, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties, has emerged as a potential therapeutic agent in accelerating burn wound healing. This study explores the efficacy of snail mucus as a novel treatment, examining its underlying mechanisms and comparative advantages over conventional burn treatments.

Methods: A comprehensive review of the literature was conducted, focusing on studies examining the effects of snail mucus on burn wound healing.

Results and Discussions: Snail mucus demonstrated significant promise in accelerating burn wound healing through multiple mechanisms. Comparative studies showed that snail mucus accelerated wound healing at a rate comparable to silver sulfadiazine. However, variability in mucus composition due to species and environmental factors remains a challenge for consistent results. Additionally, most studies have been conducted on animals, with limited human clinical trials available to confirm these findings.

Conclusion: Snail mucus exhibits significant potential as a novel treatment for burn wounds. However, the lack of standardization and the need for further human clinical trials pose challenges to its widespread clinical application. Continued research is necessary to optimize its use, establish safety protocols, and facilitate its integration into modern wound care therapies.

KEYWORDS: snail mucus, snail extract, burn, wound, healing

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I. INTRODUCTION

Burn injuries are the result of contact between the skin and a heat source, which may originate from thermal energy, electrical current, or chemical substances. The severity of burn injuries is classified into three degrees. First-degree burns, or superficial burns, involve only the epidermis of the skin. First-degree burns can heal without leaving scars within 5 to 10 days. Second-degree burns, or partial-thickness burns, involve the superficial layer of the dermis. At this stage, blisters may be present. Deep partial-thickness burns affect the deeper reticular layer of the dermis and may lead to scarring. The next classification is third-degree burns, which involve both the dermis and epidermis layers and can extend into the subcutaneous tissue. This type of burn requires

surgical treatment and typically takes around 8 weeks to heal.¹

The healing process of burn wounds involves several key phases: hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and maturation. The hemostasis phase begins immediately after the injury occurs, during which the affected tissue releases mediators such as prostaglandins and thromboxane to induce vasoconstriction. This phase also involves the activation of the coagulation cascade, resulting in the formation of fibrin fibers. Once hemostasis is achieved, the inflammatory phase follows. It is characterized by the release of histamine to increase capillary permeability and facilitate the clearance of toxins and necrotic tissue at the wound site. The proliferative phase begins approximately four days after the trauma.

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During this stage, proliferative factors are released and migrate to the wound site, promoting re-epithelialization of the basal layer and fibroblast proliferation. Finally, in the maturation phase, fibroblasts exit the wound site, and collagen is reorganized into a more structured matrix.²

The presence of burn injuries—particularly in advanced degrees—can significantly alter the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic responses to medications administered as part of therapy. An ideal therapeutic approach and wound dressing that could minimize the need for surgical intervention has yet to be fully developed and implemented on a large scale. Furthermore, the need for daily wound dressing changes by patients may reduce adherence to wound care protocols, thereby increasing the risk of complications such as infection.³

Currently, the use of natural substances for burn wound therapy is gaining popularity and widespread use among the public. The application of natural ingredients containing active compounds—such as plants, honey, and fungi—is particularly common especially in communities with limited

access to healthcare services. Snail mucus extract is one such natural substances, rich in various active compounds, with promising potential for use in burn wound therapy.^{4,5}

This study was conducted to analyze the literature in various open web databases regarding the use of snail mucus extract in burn wound healing. It also includes a discussion on the biochemical composition, mechanisms of action, and clinical potential of snail extract. This study will also addresses current limitations and provides recommendations for future research.

II. BIOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF SNAIL EXTRACT RELEVANT TO WOUND HEALING

Achatina fulica is a gastropod mollusk characterized by a conical shell and can grow up to 8 inches in length. This snail species is distributed across various regions of the world and has attracted medical research interest due to its mucus, which contains components with potential therapeutic properties.⁶

Image 1. Giant African Snail (*Achatina fulica*)⁷

The mucus of *A. fulica* contains glycosaminoglycans, allantoin, collagen, elastin, as well as anti-inflammatory compounds and antimicrobial peptides which can be beneficial in wound healing.⁸

1. Glycosaminoglycans and mucopolysaccharides

Snail mucus contains compounds such as hyaluronic acid, which is a glycosaminoglycan. Hyaluronic acid is a highly potent humectant with a helical structure that enables it to retain water up to 1000 times its own weight. This property contributes to the stabilization of the extracellular matrix and helps maintain skin hydration. The mucopolysaccharides present in snail mucus can enhance mucus adhesion to the skin. This capability can be utilized as a barrier to protect epithelial cells from pollutants and to improve the skin's viscoelasticity, thereby facilitating wound contraction.⁹

Glycosaminoglycans contribute to the acceleration of the proliferative and remodeling phases in the burn wound healing process. Mucus extract can enhance fibroblast survival, migration, and proliferation, with fibroblasts being the predominant cell type in granulation tissue. Glycosaminoglycans also exert pro-angiogenic effects through their ability to bind and stabilize angiogenic growth factors, thereby supporting tissue vascularization and improving tissue viability.¹⁰

2. Allantoin

Allantoin is an organic compound with a cyclic chemical structure comprising a urea group and a hydantoin ring. It has the ability to stimulate skin cell regeneration, enhance fibroblast proliferation, and promote the synthesis of elastin and collagen. Additionally, allantoin exhibits keratolytic effects by increasing cellular turnover. This compound can also

inhibit the migration of inflammatory cells to the wound site.^{11,12}

3. Collagen and elastin

Collagen is a vital protein component in the wound healing process. It constitutes approximately 50–90% of the integument and contributes to skin elasticity and mechanical strength. Beyond providing structural integrity and tissue resilience, collagen plays a key role in maintaining homeostasis and promoting epithelialization during wound healing. Collagen fibers assist injured tissue in regaining 50–80% of its original tensile strength prior to injury.¹³

Elastin is another key component abundantly found in the extracellular matrix. Together with microfibrils, elastin forms elastic fibers that provide the skin with stretch and recoil properties. In addition to contributing to mechanical elasticity, elastin also exerts cellular effects by reducing contraction in wounded tissue and promoting dermal regeneration. These properties help minimize scar formation and improve the flexibility of newly formed skin tissue.¹⁴

4. Antioxidant and antiinflammatory compounds

The antioxidant components found in snail mucus can help reduce oxidative stress. Selenium, in particular, can enhance plasma glutathione levels and decrease malondialdehyde (MDA) concentrations. Selenium is an essential component of the enzyme glutathione peroxidase, which protects cells from free radicals. Glutathione, along with superoxide dismutase, plays a crucial role in counteracting pro-oxidant factors originating from both exogenous and endogenous sources.^{15,16}

5. Antimicrobial peptides

Antimicrobial peptides present in snails can be utilized as anti-infective agents. These peptides exert their antimicrobial effects either directly or by modulating the immune response. Several peptides found in snail mucus, such as mytimacin-AF, have demonstrated antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as fungal species like *Candida albicans*. Fractions derived from *Achatina fulica* mucus have been shown to inhibit the growth, biofilm formation, and virulence factors of *Staphylococcus aureus*. Another peptide, achacin, exhibits bacteriostatic activity against Gram-negative bacteria. Achacin recognizes and binds to bacteria during their growth phase, subsequently activating L-amino oxidase activity, which damages the cytoplasmic membrane of the bacterial cell.¹⁷

III. MECHANISM OF ACTION IN BURN WOUND HEALING

Among them, bone marrow-derived stem cells (BMDSCs) and adipose-derived mesenchymal stem cells (AMSCs) are two types of non-skin stem cells that contribute significantly

by differentiating into approximately 20% of the fibroblasts involved in wound repair. Additionally, keratinocytes participate in the re-epithelialization phase, primarily through the differentiation of epidermal stem cells located in hair follicles. The activation of these stem cells is triggered by the release of growth factors, cytokines, and extracellular vesicles. Snail mucus has been found to stimulate specific growth factors, including basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF). These factors promote cell migration, proliferation, and angiogenesis—key processes in effective wound healing. Furthermore, snail mucus enhances the proliferation of basal epithelial cells, which contributes to faster wound closure.¹⁸

Wound healing is a complex process involving interactions among cells, growth factors, and the extracellular matrix. One of the key components of this process is angiogenesis, the formation of new blood vessels. Snail mucus has been shown to accelerate wound healing by promoting angiogenesis. This effect is largely attributed to its content of heparan sulfate, a proteoglycan that stimulates the activity of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF). The activation of VEGF leads to the development of new microvasculature, enhancing tissue regeneration. Heparan sulfate also binds and stores basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF) and interacts with other proangiogenic molecules such as FGF, PDGF, and VEGF. These interactions occur on endothelial cells, facilitating the binding of growth factors to their receptors, which in turn activates fibroblasts and promotes the formation of new capillaries at the injury site. The resulting vascular network improves oxygen supply to the damaged tissue, significantly speeding up the healing process.¹⁹

Macrophages play a crucial role in the wound healing process, primarily through their ability to switch between different functional states. Two key phenotypes involved are M1 macrophages, which are pro-inflammatory and active during the early stages of healing, and M2 macrophages, which are anti-inflammatory and promote tissue regeneration. The application of snail mucus to wounds has been shown to accelerate the transition from M1 to M2 macrophages, thereby expediting the healing process. This effect is achieved through the polarization of macrophages influenced by the bioactive components in snail mucus. Additionally, snail mucus helps reduce the expression of proinflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IFN- γ , and IL-6, further supporting a favorable environment for tissue repair and regeneration.²⁰

In addition, the mucin protein found in snail mucus has the ability to directly inhibit the enzyme cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), mimicking the anti-inflammatory mechanism of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). By reducing COX-2 activity, snail mucus helps alleviate inflammation at the wound site. Beyond its anti-inflammatory effects, snail mucus also promotes the production of collagen fibers, which supports the formation of normal scar tissue. Furthermore, it can regulate fibroblast activity, preventing

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excessive collagen deposition and thereby reducing the risk of keloid formation.²¹

Snail mucus facilitates skin regeneration by stimulating the proliferation of fibroblasts and maintaining the structural integrity of the actin cytoskeleton. Additionally, it helps regulate the activity of matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs), which are enzymes involved in extracellular matrix remodeling. By modulating MMP activity, snail mucus supports the proper assembly of the extracellular matrix. These regenerative processes are driven at the molecular level through the activation of basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF). The activation of bFGF accelerates collagen remodeling, ultimately leading to faster and more efficient wound healing.²¹

Snail slime exhibits notable antimicrobial properties, which can vary depending on the snail species, extraction techniques, and the resistance level of target microbes. Commonly studied snail species such as *Eobania desertorum* and *Helix aspersa* have demonstrated effective antimicrobial activity. Research indicates that extracts from snail slime can inhibit the growth of several pathogens frequently associated with burn infections, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Candida albicans*. Notably, studies have shown that slime from *E. desertorum* possesses stronger antimicrobial activity compared to *H. aspersa*. All gastropods secrete mucus rich in diverse proteins and bioactive compounds. Among these is methyl 1,2-benzisothiazole-3-acetate, an antiseptic compound known for its broad-spectrum antimicrobial effects.²²

Methyl 1,2-benzisothiazole-3-acetate, along with bioactive compounds like allantoin and glycolic acid found in snail mucus, contributes to its antimicrobial properties. Snail mucus is also rich in various amino acids that form antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), which make up around 70% of the peptides present. These AMPs are typically lipophilic, enhancing their ability to interact with and disrupt microbial membranes. The charged amino acids within these peptides engage directly with microbial cell membranes, leading to increased membrane permeability, depolarization, leakage of intracellular contents, cell lysis, and ultimately, cell death. Additionally, snail mucus contains a compound known as achacin, which inhibits the formation of the bacterial peptidoglycan layer. Since the peptidoglycan layer is essential for bacterial cell wall integrity, its inhibition renders bacteria more susceptible to environmental stress and immune attack.²³

IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS WITH STANDARD BURN WOUND TREATMENTS

Several effective substances are available for treating burn wounds topically, with silver sulfadiazine being one of the most commonly used agents. A study comparing silver sulfadiazine with snail mucus as a topical treatment for burn wounds found that on the first day of application, there was

no significant difference between the control group, snail mucus group, and silver sulfadiazine group. However, by day 7, the snail mucus-treated group showed a smaller wound size, comparable to the silver sulfadiazine group. The healing process for wounds treated with snail mucus showed no significant differences when compared to silver sulfadiazine, with snail mucus promoting faster healing. This accelerated healing was attributed to snail mucus's combined antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties.²⁴

Growth factor therapy is a preferred treatment for accelerating wound healing, with topical rhPDGF (recombinant human platelet-derived growth factor) being one of the most commonly used medications. This drug has demonstrated significant effectiveness in promoting faster wound healing. Other growth factors, such as rhbFGF (recombinant human basic fibroblast growth factor) and rhEGF (recombinant human epidermal growth factor), are also used for healing diabetic wounds and burns. Growth factor therapy accelerates the healing process by directly stimulating wound repair mechanisms. While the body naturally produces growth factors to facilitate healing, external growth factor therapy can expedite this process. However, a major challenge to this therapy is its high cost. Additionally, repeated high-dose applications of external growth factors can increase the risk of oncogenesis, posing safety concerns.²⁵

Snail mucus has the ability to promote the production of internal growth factors such as VEGF, bFGF, PDGF, and EGF, due to the presence of heparan sulfate, a proteoglycan found in snail mucus. This compound facilitates the binding of growth factors to their corresponding receptors, thereby accelerating the healing process. However, there is a lack of research exploring the combined use of snail mucus with external growth factor therapy, which could potentially enhance the wound healing process further.¹⁹

Wound healing time can vary significantly among patients, with comorbid conditions often disrupting the healing process, leading to increased morbidity and mortality. Stem cell therapy has shown promising results in enhancing wound healing, utilizing cells from various sources such as endothelial progenitor cells (EPC), bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BM-MSC), adipose tissue stem cells (ASC), dermal stem cells (DSC), and inducible pluripotent cells. These stem cells accelerate wound healing through tissue regeneration, employing paracrine signaling and growth factor production. These processes promote fibroblast proliferation and tissue remodeling, ultimately improving the healing outcome.²⁶

A study indicates that snail mucus from *Achatina fulica* has the potential to differentiate human mesenchymal stem cells (hMSC) into osteoblast-like cells. This effect is attributed to the presence of acharan sulfate, a glycosaminoglycan found in the mucus, which enhances osteogenic differentiation. However, there is a lack of studies exploring whether snail

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mucus can facilitate the differentiation of hMSC into other types of tissues.²⁷

Although numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of snail mucus, there is a challenge in standardizing its use. The active compounds in snail mucus vary depending on factors such as species, environment, and diet. Different snail species produce different compounds in their mucus. Most of the research on the efficacy of snail mucus has been conducted on animals, and there is a notable lack of human clinical trials. Therefore, further research is needed to identify the most effective and safe methods for using snail mucus as a topical treatment for burn wounds.²¹

V. PRECLINICAL AND CLINICAL STUDIES ON SNAIL EXTRACT IN BURN WOUND HEALING

In vitro experimental studies using mammalian fibroblast culture media have demonstrated that snail mucus possesses the ability to protect cells from apoptosis, as well as significantly induce fibroblast proliferation and migration. In fibroblast cultures induced to undergo apoptosis, the administration of snail mucus resulted in a decreased percentage of cell death. Additionally, fibroblast cultures treated with mucus showed increased growth, with the treated group reaching full confluence within 48 hours, whereas the control group only achieved a sub-confluent monolayer within the same timeframe. Snail mucus also acts as a chemoattractant stimulus, promoting more significant fibroblast migration in culture.²⁸

In addition to its effects on cell proliferation, in vitro studies using the agar well diffusion method have also demonstrated the ability of snail mucus to inhibit bacterial and fungal growth. The application of snail mucus extract to fungal strain cultures produced inhibition zones ranging from 3 ± 0.0 to 55.2 ± 0.1 mm. *Achatina fulica* mucus extract, when combined with acetic acid as a solvent, showed an inhibition zone of 19.5 ± 1.8 mm against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Similarly, cultures of *Staphylococcus aureus* exhibited an inhibition zone of 23.5 ± 2.0 mm. These findings suggest that snail mucus extract possesses notable antimicrobial potential.^{22,29}

Studies using *Mus musculus* as animal models have shown that a 5% concentration of snail mucus gel can accelerate burn wound healing, with an average healing time of 14 days—superior to the control group treated with bioplacenton. Administration of snail mucus led to a reduction in burn wound diameter from an initial size of 20 mm to 0.33 mm. Another study using histological analysis and silver sulfadiazine as a comparator also demonstrated that the rate of burn wound healing with snail mucin was significantly faster. Histopathological evaluation revealed a reduction in inflammatory cell infiltration on days 7 and 14 in the group treated with snail mucus.³⁰

A clinical study involving patients with deep partial-thickness burn injuries also demonstrated the superiority of snail extract cream compared to moist exposure burn ointment (MEBO).

The study included two groups: 27 patients with deep partial-thickness facial burns treated with snail extract cream twice daily for up to 14 days, and a control group of 16 patients treated with MEBO. The results indicated that the first group experienced faster eschar detachment, with an average time of 9 ± 2 days, whereas the control group required 11 ± 2 days. Additionally, pain levels assessed using a visual analog scale were significantly lower in the group treated with snail extract cream.³¹

VI. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS AND CLINICAL APPLICATIONS

Bioactive components found in snail mucus must be optimized to ensure their effectiveness. This optimization process begins from the collection stage and continues through to mucus processing. The method of mucus collection varies depending on the snail species used. Mucus can be collected by stimulating the snail's foot using sterile instruments such as a needle or cotton swab. Additionally, spraying with 3% NaCl solution or applying mild electric shocks can also induce mucus secretion. The mucus is then collected in sterile tubes, followed by sterilization and filtration to maintain proper pH and eliminate contaminants. More advanced extraction techniques may involve the use of natural gases, such as ozone nebulization. For preservation, the extracted mucus is stored at temperatures ranging from -80°C to -20°C or processed using lyophilization (freeze-drying) methods.⁹

The initial processed product of snail mucus can be utilized as a phytopharmaceutical by producing an extract. The composition of bioactive components in snail mucus is highly dependent on the extraction method used. Studies using filtrate extracts of snail mucus with citric acid as the medium have shown higher protein content compared to extracts obtained without stimulant solutions or those using lactic acid medium. Cytotoxicity tests indicate that the snail mucus filtrate samples are generally non-toxic to human cells, suggesting they are safe for topical application.³² Another study using a gel formulation mixed with CMC-Na in mice demonstrated that a snail mucus concentration of 96% was the most effective for wound healing.³³

In addition to its conventional use as an extract, snail mucus also holds potential for development into a hydrogel. Snail mucus-derived hydrogel features a dual-network structure, in which proteins form a three-dimensional framework alongside snail glycosaminoglycans, creating a supramolecular network. This network is reinforced by electrostatic interactions between positively charged amino or guanidine groups and the negatively charged sulfate and carboxyl groups present in the glycosaminoglycans. Divalent cations such as calcium and magnesium further influence the gel's elasticity by forming complexes, resulting in a durable and cohesive adhesive material.³⁴

Hydrogel formed from polyanionic snail glycosaminoglycan (AFG) combined with the positively charged polymer

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methacrylated gelatin (GelMA) has also been shown to enhance the wound microenvironment. This is achieved by reducing levels of inflammatory cytokines and modulating macrophage polarization toward the M2 phenotype, which promotes improved epithelialization, angiogenesis, and collagen deposition.¹⁹ In addition to hydrogel, gelatin and snail slime-based patches can also facilitate more effective delivery of mucus components to cutaneous tissues. These patches serve as controlled-release systems, enhancing the absorption and retention of bioactive compounds in the skin, thereby supporting wound healing and tissue regeneration processes more efficiently.³⁵

In addition to hydrogel and patch formulations, encapsulation with liposomes can enhance the effectiveness of snail mucus. Liposomes, formed from a mixture of phosphatidylcholine, cholesterol, and octadecylamine, can stabilize snail mucus for up to 60 days while demonstrating low cytotoxicity, making them suitable as carriers for human cells. Liposomes also improve the efficacy of snail mucus, allowing for lower dosages to achieve therapeutic effects.³⁶

The combination of *Achatina fulica* snail seromucus with chitosan has shown a synergistic immunomodulatory effect in vitro. This combination significantly enhances lymphocyte proliferation and optimizes cytokine levels, such as IFN-gamma and IL-4. Furthermore, the synergy between snail mucus and *Clitoria ternatea* extract also demonstrates promising effects in wound healing processes. This dual formulation has the potential to reduce inflammation by modulating macrophage polarization, promoting angiogenesis, and encouraging the formation of functional blood vessels.³⁷

Snail mucus has been recognized for its potential use in regenerative therapy and scar tissue healing. It promotes the proliferation and migration of keratinocytes and fibroblasts, which are essential for tissue regeneration. Studies have also shown increased expression of adhesion proteins such as E-cadherin, β -catenin, vinculin, and β 1-integrin following snail mucus application, indicating active wound healing processes. Additionally, components like lactic acid and glycolic acid have been identified in snail mucus. Glycolic acid possesses keratolytic properties, making it effective in treating scar tissue and enhancing skin cell regeneration. Lactic acid works by loosening the connections between desmosomal structures in the epidermis, thereby allowing deeper penetration of other active compounds.¹⁶

Despite the promising preclinical and early clinical evidence supporting the efficacy of snail mucin in wound healing, tissue regeneration, and scarless recovery, there remains a critical need for large-scale clinical trials and randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to validate these findings in diverse patient populations. Current data are limited by small sample sizes, lack of standardized formulations, and variability in application methods. Moreover, regulatory approval for medical use requires comprehensive toxicological profiling, pharmacokinetic studies, and quality standardization.

Addressing these gaps will pave the way for snail mucin to transition from traditional and cosmetic use into a scientifically validated, clinically approved bioactive agent in modern regenerative medicine.

VII. CONCLUSION

Snail mucus extract has demonstrated significant potential in accelerating burn wound healing, showcasing a range of regenerative, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory effects. Studies reveal that snail mucus accelerates the healing process through multiple mechanisms, including the promotion of fibroblast proliferation, enhancement of angiogenesis, and reduction of inflammation. Additionally, its antimicrobial properties contribute to effective infection control in burn wounds. When compared to conventional treatments like silver sulfadiazine, snail mucus extract has been shown to deliver comparable or even faster healing results, highlighting its promise as a novel therapeutic agent. Several limitations and challenges need to be addressed before snail mucus can be widely used in clinical settings. Mainly due to the lack of standardization in the production and composition of snail mucus. The variability in active compounds, which depends on species, environment, and diet, poses a significant obstacle in ensuring consistent therapeutic efficacy. Furthermore, there are regulatory hurdles to overcome, as snail mucus has not yet been subjected to sufficient human clinical trials. This gap in clinical evidence underlines the importance of further research to establish safety, effectiveness, and optimal usage protocols for snail mucus in burn care.

Despite these challenges, the clinical and commercial potential of snail mucus extract is considerable. If standardized and supported by robust clinical data, snail mucus could be integrated into modern burn care as a natural and effective alternative or complement to traditional treatments. Its regenerative properties could offer new possibilities in personalized wound healing strategies, where the specific needs of individual patients can be addressed with tailored treatments. Moving forward, additional human clinical trials and research into the standardization and regulatory approval of snail mucus will be crucial for its broader adoption in wound care and other regenerative medicine applications.

REFERENCES

- I. Warby R, Maani CV. Burn Classification [Internet]. Statpearls. 2023 [cited April 1 2025]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK539773/>
- II. Abazari M, Ghaffari A, Rashidzadeh, H, BADELEH S, Maleki Y. A systematic review on classification, identification, and healing process of burn wound healing. *The International Journal of Lower Extremity Wound*. 2020;21(1):1–13. doi: 10.1177/1534734620924857

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- III. Gospodarek A, Koziol M, Tobiasz M, Baj J, Büchner E, Przekora A. Burn wound healing: clinical complications, medical care, treatment, and dressing types: the current state of knowledge for clinical practice. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2022;19(3). doi: 10.3390/ijerph19031338
- IV. Moses R, Prescott T, Claret E, Steadman, R, Moseley R, Sloan A. Evidence for natural products as alternative wound-healing therapies. *Evidence for Natural Products as Alternative Wound-Healing Therapies*. *Biomolecules*. 2023;13(3). doi: 10.3390/biom13030444.
- V. Kozłowska E, Jasik K, Dziadecka D, Pol P, Trocha K, Vassev, et al. Snail mucus – a natural origin substance with potential use in medicine. *Acta Poloniae Pharmaceutica – Drug Research*. 2021;78(6):793-800. doi: 10.32383/appdr/145377
- VI. Alogna A, Liboni A, Rizzo R. Evaluation of biological properties and beneficial effects for a sustainable and conscious exploitation of *Achatina fulica* snails. *Biology*. 2025;14(2). doi: 10.3390/biology14020190
- VII. Hoffman T, Pirie N. *Achatina fulica* [Internet]. *Animal Diversity Web*. 2014 [cited April 28 2025]. Available from: https://animaldiversity.org/accounts/Achatina_fulica/
- VIII. Wargala E, Zalewska A, Slawska M, Kot I. Snail mucus as an innovative ingredient used in the cosmetology and medical industry. *Aesthetic Cosmetology and Medicine*. 2023;12(2):45-49. doi: 10.52336/acm.2023.001
- IX. Fadhilah D, Santoso P, Maliza R. 2024. Utilisation of snails for wound healing: a review. *Journal of Biodiversity and Biotechnology*. 2024;9(3). doi: 10.22146/jtbb.90236
- X. Liegertova M, Maly J. Gastropod mucus: interdisciplinary perspective on biological activities, applications, and strategic priorities. *ACS Biomaterials Science & Engineering*. 2023;9(10):5441-923. doi: 10.1021/acsbomaterials.3c01096
- XI. Dugun C. Structure and Keratolytic Properties of Allantoin. In: Cengiz GB, editors. *Current Research in Science and Mathematics*. Lyon: Livre de Lyon; 2024. p. 85-103.
- XII. Dinica RM, Sandu C, Botezatu AV, Busuioc AC, Balanescu F, Mihaila MD, Dumitru C, et al. Allantoin from valuable romanian animal and plant sources with promising anti-inflammatory activity as a nutricosmetic ingredient. *sustainability*. 2021;13(18). doi: 10.3390/su131810170
- XIII. Gardeazabal L, Izeta A. Elastin and collagen fibres in cutaneous wound healing. *Experimental Dermatology*. 2024 Feb 27;33(3). doi: 10.1111/exd.15052
- XIV. Baumann L, Bernstein EF, Weiss AS, Bates D, Humphrey S, Silberberg M, et al. Clinical relevance of elastin in the structure and function of skin. *Aesthetic Surgery Journal Open Forum*. 2021;3(3):1-8. doi: 10.1093/asjof/ojab019
- XV. Cakina S. The relationship between oxidative stress and selenium. *Environmental Toxicology and Ecology*. 2022; 2(1):21-29.
- XVI. Chen J, Liu Y, Zhao Z, Qiu J. Oxidative stress in the skin: Impact and related protection. *International Journal of Cosmetic Science*. 2021;43(5): 495-626. doi: 10.1111/ics.12728
- XVII. Singh N, Brown A, Gold M. Snail extract for skin: A review of uses, projections, and limitations. *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*. 2024; 23(4):1113-21. doi: 10.1111/jocd.16269
- XVIII. Markiewicz-Gospodarek A, Koziol M, Tobiasz M, Baj J, Radzikowska-Büchner E, Przekora A. Burn wound healing: Clinical complications, medical care, treatment, and dressing types: The current state of Knowledge for Clinical Practice. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2022;19(3). doi:10.3390/ijerph19031338
- XIX. Rosanto YB, Hasan CY, Rahardjo R, Pangestningsih TW. Effect of snail mucus on angiogenesis during wound healing. *F1000Research*. 2021;10:181. doi:10.12688/f1000research.51297.2
- XX. Deng T, Gao D, Xuemei S, Zhou Z, Zhou L, Tao M, et al. A natural biological adhesive from snail mucus for wound repair. *Nature Communications*. 2023;14(396): 1-18. doi: 10.1038/s41467-023-35907-4
- XXI. Rashad M, Sampò S, Cataldi A, Zara S. Biological activities of gastropods secretions: snail and slug slime. *Natural Products and Bioprospecting*. 2023;13(1). doi:10.1007/s13659-023-00404-0
- XXII. El-Zawawy NA, Mona, MM. Antimicrobial efficacy of Egyptian *Eremina desertorum* and *Helix aspersa* snail mucus with a novel approach to their anti-inflammatory and wound healing potencies. *Scientific Reports*. 2021;11:24317. doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-03664-3
- XXIII. Velkova L, Dolashki A, Petrova V, Pisareva E, Kaynarov D, Kermedchiev M, et al. Antibacterial properties of peptide and protein fractions from *Cornu aspersum* mucus. *Molecules*. 2024;29(12). doi:10.3390/molecules29122886
- XXIV. Song Y, Cui Y, Hao L, Zhu J, Yi J, Kang Q. Wound-healing activity of glycoproteins from white jade snail (*Achatina fulica*) on experimentally burned mice. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. 2021;175:313-21. doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2021.01.193

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- XXV. Park J, Hwang S, Yoon I-S. Advanced growth factor delivery systems in wound management and skin regeneration. *Molecules*. 2017;22(8). doi:10.3390/molecules22081259
- XXVI. Farabi B, Roster K, Hirani R, Tepper K, Atak MF, Safai B. The efficacy of stem cells in wound healing: A systematic review. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2024;25(5). doi:10.3390/ijms25053006
- XXVII. Kantawong F, Jearasakwattana T, Nira A, Chewae J, Sajjamongkol P, Phothong P, et al. PI3K/Akt signaling involved with osteoinductive effects of *Achatina Fulica Mucus*. *Brazilian Archives of Biology and Technology*. 2020;63. doi:10.1590/1678-4324-2020180501
- XXVIII. Trapella C, Rizzo R, Gallo S, Alogna A, Bortolotti D, Casciano F, et al. HelixComplex snail mucus exhibits pro-survival, proliferative, and pro-migration effects on mammalian fibroblasts. *Scientific Reports*. 2018;8:17665. doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-35816-3
- XXIX. Okeniyi FA, Oghenochuko OM, Olawoye SO, Animashahun RA, Adeyonu AG, Akpor OB. Antimicrobial potentials of mucus mucin from different species of giant African land snails on some typed culture pathogenic bacteria. *Asian Journal of Agricultural & Biology*. 2022;4:1-12. doi: 10.35495/ajab.2021.07.294
- XXX. Harlis WO, Adi DA, Saraswati NM, Jamili, Suriana, Resman. Effectiveness of snail mucus gel (*Achatina fulica Ferr*) on mice (*Mus musculus L.*) burns. *Jurnal Pijar MIPA*. 2023;18(3):425-529. doi: 10.29303/jpm.v18i3.4803
- XXXI. Tsoutsos D, Kakagia D, Tamparopoulos K. The efficacy of *Helix aspersa Muller* extract in the healing of partial thickness burns: a novel treatment for open burn management protocols. *Journal of Dermatological Treatment*. 2009;20(4): 219-22. doi: doi.org/10.1080/09546630802582037
- XXXVIII. 2.
- XXXII. Filippo MF, Dolsi LS, Bonvicini F, Sparla F, Gentilomi GA, Panzavolta S, et al. Influence of the extraction method on functional properties of commercial snail secretion filtrates. *Scientific Reports*. 2024;14(1):22053. doi: 10.1038/s41598-024-72733-0
- XXXIII. Rosanto YB, Hasan CY, Rahardjo, Surya A. The potential of snail (*Achatina fulica*) mucus gel as a phytopharmaca to accelerate the inflammation process during wound healing. *World Journal of Dentistry*. 2022;13(3):224-27. doi: doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10015-2056
- XXXIV. Zhou Z, Deng T, Tao M, Lin L, Sun L, Song X, et al. Snail-inspired AFG/GelMA hydrogel accelerates diabetic wound healing via inflammatory cytokines suppression and macrophage polarization. *Biomaterials*. 2023;299. doi: 10.1016/j.biomaterials.2023.122141
- XXXV. Di Filippo MF, Albertini B, Dolci LS, Bonvicini F, Bigi A, Gentilomi GA, et al. Novel drug-loaded film forming patch based on gelatin and snail slime. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2021;598. doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2021.120408
- XXXVI. Alogna A, Gentili V, Trapella C, Hallan SS, Sguizzato M, Strazzabosco G, et al. Design of liposomes carrying HelixComplex snail mucus: preliminary studies. *Molecules*. 2021;26(16). doi: 10.3390/molecules26164709
- XXXVII. Apritrycia E, Dirayati M, Wassi'atu NA, Setiawan R, Maras MA, Endah. Combination of *Achatina fulica* snail mucus and *Clitoria ternatea* extracts in wound healing potential to accelerating the minor inflammatory phase: a review. In: Lee HL, Yazid H, Ibrahim F, editors. 6th International Conference on Biomedical Engineering. Cham: Springer. 2023. p.570-58